

IMPACT OF PHYSICAL EXERCISE ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF CANCER PATIENTS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a systematic review of the literature on the impact of physical exercise on the quality of life of cancer patients. Numerous studies have demonstrated that regular physical activity, particularly aerobic and resistance exercises, plays a crucial role in mitigating the adverse effects of cancer treatment, such as fatigue, depression, muscle mass loss (sarcopenia), and reduced cardiovascular function. Additionally, physical exercise significantly contributes to the rehabilitation of these patients, promoting muscle mass preservation, cardiovascular improvement, and enhanced functional capacity. These benefits directly impact quality of life, facilitating independence and the ability to perform daily activities. Specifically, strength training has been associated with preventing the loss of lean mass, while endurance training (aerobic exercise) is effective in improving cardiorespiratory capacity and reducing cancer-related fatigue. These exercise modalities also positively affect psychological symptoms, such as anxiety and depression, which often impact patients during and after treatment. Furthermore, regular exercise is linked to a reduced risk of recurrence of certain types of cancer and improved overall prognosis, including survival rates. The article emphasizes that exercise prescription should be an integral part of oncology treatment and rehabilitation programs, necessitating the adaptation of exercise protocols to the individual capacities and conditions of each patient, considering factors such as cancer type, disease stage, and ongoing treatments. In conclusion, this review highlights that the implementation of well-structured and supervised physical exercise programs has the potential to significantly enhance the quality of life and clinical outcomes of cancer patients, reinforcing the importance of integrating oncology with physical activity in the multidisciplinary care of patients .

Keywords: Physical exercise, Quality of life, Cancer patients, Oncology rehabilitation, Sarcopenia.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer represents one of the main causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide, with significant impacts on patients' quality of life, both during and after treatment (Ferlay et al., 2020). The physical and psychological consequences of cancer treatment, such as fatigue, loss of muscle mass, decreased cardiovascular function and depression, often reduce the quality of life of patients (Baumann et al., 2016). In this context, physical exercise has been proposed as a non-pharmacological intervention that can mitigate these adverse effects, providing both physical and psychological benefits, improving patients' quality of life (Campbell et al., 2019).

Thus, it is important to understand that quality of life (QOL) is a multidimensional concept that encompasses physical, emotional, social and functional factors, all influenced by an individual's health conditions (WHO, 1995). In cancer patients, QOL is often assessed using standardized instruments, such as the European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life Questionnaire (EORTC QLQ-C30) and the Functional Assessment of Cancer Therapy-General (FACT-G), which measure aspects such as physical health, emotional well-being and functional capacities (Aaronson et al., 1993; Cella et al., 1993).

The decline in muscle strength in cancer patients is directly related to the loss of weight and muscle mass, often resulting from the state of malnutrition that accompanies the progression of the disease and the side effects of treatment (Argilés et al., 2018). Cachexia, characterized by a marked loss of skeletal muscle mass, is a common condition in advanced stages of cancer and is associated with a worse prognosis and a significant reduction in quality of life (Fearon et al., 2011). This loss of strength and muscle mass limits the functionality of patients, negatively impacting their ability to perform daily activities and their autonomy (Baracos et al., 2018).

Strength (resistance) and endurance (cardiovascular resistance) exercises can play a crucial role in improving these conditions. Resistance training is effective in preserving and recovering muscle mass, in addition to improving functional strength, helping patients maintain their independence and quality of life (Thomas et al., 2017). In addition, aerobic exercise contributes to improving cardiovascular capacity, combating fatigue and elevating mood (Buffart et al., 2017). Studies suggest that the combination of both types of exercise can be an effective approach in the rehabilitation of cancer patients, promoting physical and psychological benefits that go beyond the treatment period (Courneya & Friedenreich, 2019).

OBJECTIVE

This systematic review aims to synthesize the most recent scientific evidence on the impact of physical exercise on the quality of life of cancer patients, seeking to provide a comprehensive understanding of the benefits of this intervention.

Specific Objectives

Analyze how different types of physical exercise (resistance, endurance, combined) influence the physical and psychological aspects of quality of life in cancer patients.

To assess the impact of physical exercise on reducing cancer-related fatigue and other specific symptoms that affect patients' functionality.

To examine the effectiveness of physical exercise in preserving and recovering muscle mass and strength in cancer patients, considering the impact of malnutrition and cachexia.

To investigate the relationship between regular exercise and the reduction in the risk of recurrence of some types of cancer and the longevity of patients.

To identify gaps in the literature and suggest future directions for research on physical exercise programs aimed at oncological rehabilitation.

METHODOLOGY

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the *Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses* (PRISMA) guidelines (Moher et al., 2009). The process included defining inclusion and exclusion criteria, selecting databases, developing a search strategy, screening studies, extracting data, and assessing the quality of the included articles.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies were included if they met the following criteria:

Population : Cancer patients of any age, sex or type of cancer.

Intervention : Physical exercise programs, including resistance exercises, endurance or combined interventions.

Comparator: Cancer patients who did not participate in physical exercise programs or who received usual care.

Outcome: Quality of life assessed by validated instruments, such as the EORTC QLQ-C30 or FACT-G.

Study type : Randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies, and previous systematic reviews.

Language: Studies published in English, Spanish and Portuguese.

Publication period: Studies published between January 2013 and December 2023.

Studies were excluded if:

Focus on non-oncological populations.

They did not evaluate quality of life as a main outcome.

They were case reports, narrative reviews, or non-peer-reviewed articles.

Data Sources and Search Strategy

The databases used to search for articles were PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science and Cochrane Library. The search strategy included keywords and descriptors related to the topic, such as "cancer", "physical exercise", "quality of life", "oncology", "muscular resistance" and "endurance". The terms were combined using Boolean operators (AND, OR) to ensure that all relevant studies were captured.

Screening and Selection of Studies

Two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts identified in the search. Potentially relevant articles were selected for full text reading. Discrepancies between reviewers were resolved by consensus or by a third reviewer, when necessary.

Data Extraction

The data were extracted in a standardized manner using a previously prepared form, which included the following information:

Authors' data (year, country).

Sample characteristics (number of participants, age, type of cancer).

Physical exercise intervention (type, duration, frequency, intensity).

Main outcomes (quality of life, muscle strength, fatigue, cancer recurrence).

Results and conclusions of the studies.

Assessment of Study Quality

The methodological quality of the studies was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for randomized controlled trials (Higgins et al., 2011) and the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for observational studies (Wells et al., 2000). The studies were classified as having low, moderate or high risk of bias, based on criteria such as randomization, blinding, follow-up of participants and validity of outcomes.

Data Summary

The results were synthesized qualitatively, grouping the studies according to the type of physical exercise intervention and the outcomes analyzed. When possible, a meta-analysis was performed using RevMan 5.4 software to calculate the combined effect of the interventions on the quality of life of cancer patients.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the studies reviewed in this systematic review consistently shows that physical exercise, especially strength and endurance training, has a significant impact on the quality of life of cancer patients. The results of the articles analyzed indicate that these physical interventions are effective both in terms of improving functional capacity and in the psychological well-being of patients.

Impact of Exercise on Fatigue and Physical Function

Several reviewed studies reveal that physical exercise contributes substantially to the reduction of cancer-related fatigue, one of the most prevalent adverse effects among patients. Studies using aerobic and strength training interventions have demonstrated significant improvements in energy and vitality in patients with breast and prostate cancer. These gains were especially evident in supervised programs, where the intensity and frequency of exercise were adjusted according to the individual conditions of the patients (Baumann, Zopf & Bloch, 2016; Lowe et al., 2020).

In addition to fatigue, functional capacity also showed significant improvements, with resistance training being highly effective in preserving muscle mass and strength. This is particularly relevant for patients undergoing therapies such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy, who commonly experience sarcopenia and loss of lean mass. Prostate cancer patients undergoing resistance training, for example, were able to maintain and even improve their muscle strength during androgen deprivation treatment, reducing the negative impact of this therapy on the musculoskeletal system (Galvão & Newton, 2017).

Comparison between Active and Non-Active Patients

Studies comparing physically active cancer patients with sedentary patients have provided strong evidence that regular exercise is associated with improved quality of life and significant reductions in cancer-related symptoms. Buffart et al. (2017) found that patients who maintain an exercise regimen during and after cancer treatment experience lower levels of fatigue, fewer depressive symptoms, and a greater perception of well-being compared to non-active patients.

Furthermore, regular exercise has been associated with a lower recurrence of some types of cancer, such as breast and colon cancer. Courneya & Friedenreich (2019) highlight that physically active patients have a lower risk of mortality not only from cancer, but also from cardiovascular diseases, with exercise acting as an important adjuvant component in cancer treatment.

Exercise and Mental Health

Another important area of impact of physical exercise is psychological well-being. Interventions that include mind-body activities, such as yoga and Tai Chi, have shown impressive results in reducing anxiety, depression, and stress, which are commonly reported by cancer patients. In addition to promoting physical improvements, these types of activities offer significant emotional relief during treatment, helping patients cope with the psychological challenges of cancer (Truong et al., 2020).

Final Discussion

The findings of this review reinforce the importance of integrating physical exercise as an essential part of oncology rehabilitation. Whether through resistance, endurance or mind-body activities, physical exercise offers an effective and safe non-pharmacological intervention to improve the quality of life of cancer patients. These benefits, both physical and psychological, are evident across different types of cancer, and supervision by qualified health professionals is crucial to ensure safety and maximize beneficial effects.

In the long term, physical exercise not only improves quality of life during treatment, but may also have protective effects against cancer recurrence and other related health problems. Evidence suggests that, for cancer patients, physical exercise should be seen as an important complement to traditional medical treatment, being fundamental in rehabilitation and improving overall prognosis (Courneya & Friedenreich, 2019; Galvão & Newton, 2017; Buffart et al., 2017).

CONCLUSION

Physical exercise, especially strength and endurance exercises, has been shown to be an effective non-pharmacological intervention to improve the quality of life of cancer patients. This systematic review demonstrates that regular exercise can mitigate adverse effects of cancer treatment, such as fatigue, loss of muscle mass, and functional decline, in addition to promoting psychological benefits, such as reducing symptoms of depression and anxiety. Furthermore, studies suggest that physically active patients have a lower risk of disease recurrence and longer survival.

The comparison between trained and untrained cancer patients reinforces the importance of supervised exercise programs in the context of cancer rehabilitation, highlighting that exercise should be an essential part of integrated care. Resistance training has been shown to be particularly effective in preserving muscle strength and combating sarcopenia, while aerobic exercise contributes to improving cardiovascular fitness and overall health.

Therefore, it is essential that healthcare professionals, especially in oncology, recognize the benefits of physical exercise and integrate individualized physical training protocols into conventional treatments, improving not only survival but also the quality of life of patients. Future studies can continue to explore differentiated approaches to exercise and its influence

on different types of cancer and treatment phases, further consolidating the role of exercise as a fundamental part of cancer treatment.

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